

EDUCATIONAL GAMES ORGANIZED IN 3RD-4TH GRADE MOTHER TONGUE CLASSES AND PECULIARITIES OF THEIR USE

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Abstract: In this article, educational games used in 3rd-4th grade mother tongue lessons, their content, effectiveness and methodology are analyzed based on specific sources.

Key words: Theme, complexity, composition, child, environment, environment, natural phenomena, scenery, objects, plants, animal world, morality, physical aspect, etc.

Introduction: Morphological materials are widely studied in elementary grades. During four years of study, students will gain some knowledge about the word and its meanings, word form, morphological structure of the word. and acquires theoretical and more practical knowledge on his own character.

Primary school mother tongue curriculums are structured based on the principle of a stepwise sequence, taking into account the characteristics of students, their mental, moral and physical growth from year to year. Based on this, the part of each subject that is easily mastered by students is studied in the lower grades, and the more complex part is studied in the next grades. Some word groups are studied in all grades of primary education. First of all, its main sign is studied, which means the name, sign, number and movement of an object, and the additional sign is mastered, as well as how to answer a question based on the acquired knowledge. As the students progress from grade to grade, they learn the specific signs of word groups. Such study of educational material requires repetition of knowledge acquired in one class in subsequent classes.

Review of the literature: The knowledge given to the student is based on the knowledge of the children in the previous classes. This makes it possible to organize various grammar games based on the student's previous knowledge. Because the student can actively participate in the organized grammar game only when there is a certain level of knowledge and skills on the subject. On the other hand, the student takes a creative approach to the training based on the knowledge he has and performs activities.

In morphology, students learn the similarities and differences between each grammatical phenomenon. Different grammar games can be organized by

comparing them. Such an activity can be used in every lesson devoted to the study of morphology. For example, it is possible to compare nouns with a similar noun when passing them, and to compare them when passing agreeable adverbs. you can organize a grammar game with the help of the suffix.

In elementary grades, the term word is used instead of morphology. Pupils also learn lexicology and word formation knowledge in the vocabulary section, so we considered it necessary to provide games related to the above sections of linguistics in the complex of morphological games.

"Find the foreign word" game

This game encourages you to pay attention to the dictionary meaning of the word. Strengthens the student's memory. Gets used to thinking quickly and answering quickly. It can be conducted on various topics. When playing such a game, words that have the same commonality are chosen.

1. Tashkent, Andijan, Karshi, Termiz, Baku. (Baku is a foreign word. All cities are located in Uzbekistan, and Baku is outside our country).
2. Oybek, Hamid Olimjon, Babur, Gafur Ghulam, Kamil Yashin. (Foreign word- Babur. All of them lived and created in the 20th century, and Babur is a representative of classical literature).
3. A bus, a car, a tractor, an airplane, a motorcycle (Plane is a foreign word. Others walk on the ground. An airplane flies to the sky).
4. Noun, adjective, number, pronoun, participle, verb. (the participle is foreign. All words indicate groups of words. The participle is a part of a sentence).

"Find the place of the word" game

This game is held in order to strengthen the learned rules about capitalization of famous nouns. Through the game, the spelling of names and surnames of people and places with capital letters is strengthened. Before the game, students are given cards. A poem or sentence can be written on the cards. Capitalized words in bold text are omitted.

A second card is given to the student. The words that were dropped were written on it. The student must read the omitted words in place of the dots according to the meaning of the sentence. The child who correctly reads the omitted word is the winner of the game.

1. card

... .. *first in the mother tongue*

... *they wrote (five epics). SHE IS.... was born.*

Omitted words: "Hamsa" in Herat, Alisher Navoi

2. card.

... he sat on his father's throne at the age of twelve and wrote a work called ... He ... died.

Omitted words: "Baburnoma" in Babur, India.

After the students have played the game a couple of times and gained a certain level of skill, other words can be mixed up on both cards. Sometimes it is possible to write the words written on both cards on the same card. This will teach the student to choose the right noun. The student who completes the task quickly and correctly will be the winner of the game and will be encouraged.

Such a game can be organized in the way of reading by putting the omitted words in their place. During the game, children pay attention to the meaning of the word. Below are poems with two stanzas, both stanzas of which are given to two students. The omitted words are given in full on both cards. The student chooses the right word.

1st card

2nd card

Smallpox

Muhammadjon Koshakov's poem.

<i>U ochildi ... chog'ida</i>	<i>Qarab tursam, u gunafsha,</i>
<i>Erka chechak, oy chechak.</i>	<i>. . . ham suluvroq.</i>
<i>. . . deb ataladi,</i>	<i>. . . keldi deb chorlovchi,</i>
<i>Gullar ichra kelinchak.</i>	<i>G o'yoki . . . qo'ng'iroq.</i>

Omitted words: *Loladan Boychechak, jajji, tong bahor.*

Mehmon

Olobergan Polat's poem

<i>1st card</i>	<i>2nd card.</i>
<i>Bog'da... dugona</i>	<i>Patnis bezadi.... ,</i>
<i>Hulkar bilan... .</i>	<i>Olma,, konfet qo'yib.</i>
<i>Ikkalasi o'tirib,</i>	<i>O'yin bahonasida</i>
<i>. . . mehmon-mehmon.</i>	<i>Zeboxon.... to'yib.</i>

Omitted words: *inoq, o'ynadi, oldi, nok, Zeboxon, Hulkar.*

Students play this game as follows.

1st card

2nd card

Smallpox

Muhammadjon Koshakov's poem.

U ochildi tong chog'ida *Qarab tursam, u gunafsha,*
Erka chechak, oy chechak. *Loladan ham suluvroq.*
Boychechak deb ataladi, *Bahor keldi deb chorlovchi,*
Gullar ichra kelinchak. *Go'yoki jajji qo'ng'iroq.*

Mehmon

Ollobergan Po'lat she'ri

1-kartochka

Bog'da inoq dugona

Hulkar bilan Zeboxon.

Ikkalasi o'tirib,

O'ynadi mehmon-mehmon.

2-kartochka.

Patnis bezadi Hulkar,

Olma, nok, konfet qo'yib.

O'yin bahonasida

Zeboxon oldi to'yib.

Work on synonyms and antonyms

CONCLUSION: Elementary school students get to know the dictionary meanings of words practically from the 1st grade. In order to form their knowledge, various independent activities are carried out. In order to strengthen students' knowledge of synonyms, antonyms, and homonyms, and to increase their interest, a number of grammar games can be used that encourage children to think, reason, and compare words.

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